

RESOURCES OF THE TOURIST TERRITORY: NATURE, COMPOSITION AND ROLE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC SYSTEM

Allayorov Ravshan Alievich

Basic doctoral student of Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7550141>

Abstract. *The article provides a scientific and theoretical analysis of the definitions of the concept of "tourist resources" given by foreign and domestic scientists, based on the grouping of different approaches. Based on the results of the analysis, the composition of tourist resources was determined, and an author's definition of this concept was developed.*

Keywords: *tourism, tourist resources, recreational resources, two-factor approach, three-factor approach, natural-climatic conditions, infrastructure.*

Introduction

In recent years, in the context of globalization of international relations, integration processes in the world economy are constantly under the influence of deintegration factors (increasing number of "conflict points" around the world, the introduction and intensification of socio-economic sanctions, the spread of various diseases, etc.). At the end of December 2019, the spread of COVID-2019 in China was recorded, which has forced the whole world to change its attitude to socio-economic policy to this day. The global impact of the coronavirus epidemic has posed a serious threat to all aspects of the world - economic, social development and other areas. This impact has had a significant impact on the economic situation of airlines, especially in the field of tourism and hospitality.

Tourism has been noted as one of the leading sectors of the world economy for the last twenty years, and its growth rates and share in global macroeconomic indicators have led to its recognition as a future industry. These trends have become the basis for comprehensive reforms aimed at developing the tourism sector as a leading sector of the national economy in Uzbekistan, which has a high tourism potential. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoev dated December 2, 2016 No. PF-4861 "On measures to ensure the accelerated development of the tourism sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan" provides for the restructuring and diversification of the national economy. A number of tasks aimed at accelerating the development of tourism as one of the powerful tools to deepen employment, increase incomes and quality of life and make tourism one of the strategic sectors of our economy have been identified, and the main priorities have been identified.

More than 70 normative and legal acts adopted in 2016-2019 have created the primary and necessary conditions for the rapid development of the tourism industry in our country. Reforms aimed at developing the tourism sector as a strategic sector of the national economy have yielded positive results. The number of foreign visitors to Uzbekistan has been growing steadily every year. Thus, in 2019, the Republic of Uzbekistan was visited by 6748 thousand foreign tourists, which is 26.2% more than in 2018.

By the 21st century, tourism has become a way of life for everyone and has the potential to recover quickly after political, economic and social crises. Therefore, one of the most pressing

issues today is the revival of the tourism industry and the rapid economic reforms in the field, based on the current sanitary and epidemiological situation in the world.

From this point of view, scientific research on the content and essence of the concepts inherent in the tourism system, in particular, the concept of "tourist resource" is relevant today.

Literature review

The economic literature studies theoretical and methodological issues specific to various aspects of tourism development. In particular, the theoretical foundations and practical issues of economic relations inherent in the tourism economy, tourism market economy, as well as specific issues of the use of tourist resources were studied by scientists from the CIS countries VI Azar, IT Balabanov, A.Yu. Alexandrova, V.S. Bogolyubov, M.B.Birjakov, M.N.Dmitriev, A.B.Zdorov, N.B.Zorin, V.A.Kvartalnov.

A.Yu.Aleksandrova, A.M.Gavrilov, N.N.Zubakova, P.I.Karanevsky, A.S.Kuskov, M.A.Morozov, studied the elements of resource potential of regions for the development of recreation and tourism. I.Mukhina, I.I.Pirozhnik, V.S.Prebrajensky, N.S.Mironenko, I.T.Tverdokhlebov and similar scientists made a great contribution.

Specific issues of tourism development in Uzbekistan KH Abdurahmanov, EV Golisheva, NS Ibragimov, MK Paradaev, AF Saidov, B.Sh. Safarov, T. Tashmurotov, N. Tukhliev, IS Tukhliev, BH Turaev, DK Usmanova, OH Khamidov, MT Alimova and a number of other economists.

Research methodology

Since the purpose of the study was based on the coverage of the theoretical and methodological foundations of the topic, theoretical research methods were used to shed light on the theoretical foundations of the tourism area.

Analysis and results.

The use of the concept of "tourist resource" is accepted in the scientific literature on tourism. Tourism resources are the basis for creating a tourism product. Analyzing the views of different authors on the nature and elements of tourist resources, we can conclude that there is no consensus on this issue. In some sources, the concepts of "tourist resource" and "recreational resource" are considered as interrelated concepts, while in some sources, these resources are interpreted as the same concept, which requires clarification of the definition of these concepts.

Recreational resources are interpreted as the sum of natural-climatic, domestic, cultural, health-improving, educational, historical and other similar resources used or intended to be used in the provision of recreational services in the course of recreational activities [1]. Table 1 lists a number of definitions of "tourist resources". In our view, the concepts cited do not fully disclose the economic content of these resources, which in turn implies certain definitions. We propose to consider tourism resources in terms of their impact on the socio-economic development of the regions.

The tourist resources of the region are a specific type of resource and require special approaches to their classification. The classification of tourist resources has been carried out by scientists at different stages of development of the tourism industry. In particular, the Polish economist M. Trausi (1963) divides tourist resources into three groups: natural (climate, air, landscape, sea, river, mountains, forest, etc.); resources created by human labor (architectural structures, sculptures, works of art, etc.) and additional (resources created by human labor for the purpose of service-infrastructure).

Table 1

Basic concepts of tourist resources

Contents	Name of source	Authors
Although Article 17 of the law recognizes tourist resources as natural, historical, socio-cultural, medical and health facilities, as well as other facilities that can meet the needs of tourists and excursionists, they are not explained as a separate article.	Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Tourism	Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, No. O'RQ-549 of 18.07.2019
A complex of cultural-historical, socio-economic and natural objects that can be used in tourism	Tourism, service and hospitality	L.P. Voronkova
Natural-climatic, socio-cultural, historical and similar resources of the region, which is a factor of the tourist microenvironment and creates a tourist impression, able to meet the interests of tourism	Practical touring	G.A. Avanesova
Objects and events such as natural-climatic, socio-cultural, historical and archeological, scientific and industrial, spectacular, architectural, which are able to meet the goals and needs of man in the field of tourism	The role of tourist resources in the development of tourism	V.I. Maslov
A set of natural-climatic, socio-cultural and infrastructural factors of the region used in the production of tourist products to meet the goals and needs of man in the field of tourism	Development of regional tourism on the basis of tourism resource management strategy	A.I. Frolov

French economist P. Defer (1972) believes that infrastructure facilities are not part of tourist resources. It divides tourist resources into four groups: hydro (water bodies); fitom (er, nature); lithom (man-made architectural buildings and structures); anthropom (intangible human activities - customs, holidays, rituals, values, etc.) [2]. A number of researchers support the views of P. Defer, including M.E. Nemolyaev, L.F. ... while these businesses provide access to tourism resources, they cannot serve as a tourist destination on their own. ” We cannot agree with P. Defer’s views: In our view, infrastructure facilities are part of the resource element needed to create a tourism product.

SA Bystrov and MG Vorontsova have a different opinion on the composition of the elements of tourist resources. They include in the classification of tourist resources natural and tourist interest, direct tourist resources, infrastructure resources, as well as resources of tourism production factors (financial, information, labor, education, material, etc.). The views of MM Amirkhanova, NS Lukashina, AP Trunev on the composition of the elements of tourist resources are of particular interest. They include complex tourist resources (resources of natural-territorial tourist institutions), natural-continental and natural-aqual, natural-anthropogenic (parks, alleys, forest parks, national parks) and unique and unique (natural parks) consisting of natural areas such as nature reserves, river valleys. natural monuments). LV Gorkanova summarizes the main approaches to the classification of tourist resources [3]. According to him, the classification of tourist resources can be made on the following criteria:

- general (in terms of origin, recovery capacity, unusability or complete loss rate);
- by the composition of resources (description of use, functional suitability (use in its intended direction), the ability to replace one resource with another);
- on the quality of tourist products (level of convenience, aesthetic appeal, importance);
- by prevalence in the region;
- According to the intensity of use.

Analyzing certain approaches to the classification of tourist resources, the author suggests the use of a classification conducted by researcher N.P. Krachilo on the composition of resources and fully covering all elements of the natural and economic potential of the region. In this case, the author proposes to replace the first group of "natural resources" with "natural-climatic resources", and to expand socio-economic resources based on the classification proposed by S.A. Bystrova and M.G. Vorontsova. In addition, it is proposed to divide the group of socio-economic resources into subgroups of "infrastructure", "organizational and managerial resources" (education, personnel, management, material, financial, information, institutional resources).

As noted above, a number of authors do not include infrastructure tourism resources in the group of socio-economic resources, preferring to consider such resources as a separate group. In our opinion, it is expedient to include tourism infrastructure in the group of socio-economic resources, as it is tourism infrastructure that is an important link in the creation of tourism products and the main resource for the development of the tourism industry. It is also necessary to replenish the group of socio-economic resources with elements of the institutional environment.

Systematic scientific research on the flow of tourists and the placement of recreational resources began in the 70s of the last century, such research includes M.A. Ananov, 1975; N.S. Falkovich, 1972; P.T.Lixanov, 1973 such as work done by scientists.

The first description of recreational resources was given by a number of scientists from the Institute of Geography under the direction of V.S. Preobrazhensky. While the resources are interpreted from a natural-geographical point of view, their study relies on an assessment of the natural-landscape environment of recreation and leisure.

It should be noted that in the early stages of the study of this object as a resource there are a number of scientific works that consider only natural constituents (A.A. Mikhailov et al., 1971; U.K. Savelev, T.S. Shchitov, 1977 y.) [4]. The growth of tourist activity of the population, the wider involvement of new natural and other tourist resources in the process of circulation. By the 1980s, there was a need for a systematic study of recreational tourism, taking into account the technical and economic indicators. It should be noted that the research in the field of tourism was initially characterized by a strong emphasis on the geographical aspects of the industry, but later these studies have become more in-depth, taking into account the social and economic aspects. In this case, recreational resources are considered in terms of their ability to exhibit positive features in terms of time and space, ie not only in terms of functional convenience (suitability in terms of organizing recreational activities), but also in terms of territorial and temporal convenience. In terms of time, convenience reflects the duration of functionally favorable conditions, while regional convenience refers to the size of the area with favorable opportunities for recreation. This interpretation of recreational resources is described in the scientific monograph of NS Mironenko, M. Bochvarova (1986). explained [4].

According to most authors and researchers, the general aspect of tourist resources is that they reflect objects and events of natural-anthropogenic character, whether directly or indirectly related to the needs (goals and interests) of tourists.

The specifics of the approaches to defining the concept of "tourist resources" are reflected in their composition, integrity and specificity to a particular region. In our study, we divided the definitions of the concept of "tourist resources" into three groups.

1. Approaches to the description of tourist resources in terms of their composition. Some authors refer to these resources as two enlarged groups of internal factors - natural and socio-cultural factors: "natural and cultural landscapes" (I.I. Pirozhnik, E.L. Plisetsky), "natural elements and specific results of human activity" (P. Deffer), "natural and cultural-historical objects" (G.A. Karpova, Glossary of tourist terms). A number of other authors believe that such resources should include historical, architectural, archeological, religious, scientific, exhibition facilities (D.S.Ushakov, V.I.Azar, V.N.Akishin, etc.). , but it should be noted that, in essence, these resources are a practical result of the socio-cultural activities of society. For this reason, these definitions reflect a two-factor approach to the interpretation of tourism resources.

Another approach to determining the composition of tourist resources is based on the separation of three groups of factors - natural, socio-cultural and infrastructural (logistical).

In our opinion, the first approach to defining the concept of tourist resources is a bit narrow and does not fully reveal the essence of this concept. We will try to explain this by the regularity shown in the definitions given. This law is manifested in the form of interrelationships between criteria such as "content" and "conditions of transfer".

2. An approach to defining tourist resources in terms of the interrelationships of tourist elements. In addition to differences in the definition of the composition of tourist resources, there are also some differences in their interpretation. The following differences are related to the interdependence of tourism resource elements.

In particular, I.I. If researchers such as Pirozhnik, P. Deffer, E.L. Plisetsky consider individual objects that serve the needs of tourists as resource-forming factors; Authors such as G.P.Dolzhenko, O.O.Baydik, V.G.Gulyaev, I.N.Gavrilchak interpret the interaction as a tourist resource, rather than individual elements of natural-anthropogenic character that meet the needs of tourism.

Table 2

The structure of tourist resources in the scientific work of foreign researchers

Two-factor approach:	A three-factor approach: Nature + socio-cultural + infrastructure
----------------------	--

<p><i>Nature + socio-cultural</i> Yu.B. Xramov, V.A. Klyushkin, 1976: -natural; -cultural. Yu.A. Vedenin, V.N. Kozlov, 1995: -natural; -cultural-enlightenment. Yu.S. Putrik, A.V. Gitbut, 1995: -natural; -cultural-historical. A.B. Shtogrin, 2000: -natural; -socio-cultural. V.V. Xrabovchenko, 2003: -natural; -social; -cultural-historical</p>	<p><i>R.Grande, 1993;</i> <i>N.I. Kabushkin, 1999;</i> <i>A.Yu. Aleksandrova, 2001;</i> <i>I.A. Revinskiy, L.S. Romanova, 2001;</i> <i>A.G. Nizamiev, 2003:</i> -natural; -socio-cultural; -infrastructure. Yu.V. Lisauskayte, 2000 y .: -touristic; -curortological; -health; -material. T.K. Sergeeva, 2004: -natural landscape; -cultural landscape; -infrastructure.</p>
---	--

In the organization, planning and control of production activities at the level of tourism firms or on a micro scale, resources are considered as separate objects or their various ratios used in the creation of a tourist product. In determining the consumption value of tourist products and creating an image in this regard, the integration of factors used to meet the complex needs of tourists and used in the production of resources is used.

1. Approach to the definition of tourist resources in terms of their dependence on tourist areas. At the same time, most researchers do not use the practice of "linking" tourist resources to a particular area in determining them. It should be noted that it is impossible to organize production activities by moving tourist resources from one place to another. Therefore, we support the approach put forward by researchers such as EL Plisetsky, G.P. Dolzhenko, G. Harris, O.O. Baydik, I.N. Gavrilchik and D.S.Ushakov. The above-mentioned researchers recommend the study of tourist resources "linking" to a particular area the factors that allow to create tourist products and meet the needs of tourists. In addition, from the point of view of regional tourism, it is important to "attach" resources to the region, because regional resources are available in a limited way and reflect the state of a specific area of the region. The ability of a region to meet the needs of tourists is determined by the composition and quality of the resource factors available within the region.

Conclusion and recommendations

Summarizing the results of the analysis, we can highlight the criteria that can be used to determine the regional tourist resources:

1. Complexity description - "generality of factors of natural and anthropogenic characterization";
2. Content - "natural-climatic, historical-cultural and socio-economic factors";
3. Territorial affiliation - "factors that own or exist in a particular territory";
4. Conditions of carrying out - "Possibilities of use in production of the tourist product on satisfaction of needs in the purpose and process of tourism".

In conclusion, regional tourist resources are a complex set of natural-climatic, historical-cultural and socio-economic factors of the region used in the development of tourist products to meet the needs of the visitor in the implementation of tourist goals.

REFERENCES

1. Pisarevsky E. The development of tourism and the tourist industry in the European Union / E. Pisarevskiy. // *Tourism: law and economics*. - 2005.-№1.-S. 16-29.
2. Kartashevskaya I. F. Optimization of management processes of tourist resources at the regional level / I. F. Kartashevskaya // *Culture of the peoples of the Black Sea region*. - 2003. - JV "45. - S. 49-52.
3. Gorkanova, L. V. Theoretical approaches to the classification of tourist resources of the region [Text] / L. V. Gorkanova // *Bulletin of the Orenburg State University*. - No. 8 (196). - 2014. - S. 79–83.
4. *Recreational systems. monograph* / ed. N. S. Mironenko, M. Bochvarova. - M. : Publishing House of Moscow State University, 1986. - 136 p.
5. Khromov Yu.B. Organization of recreation and tourism areas on the coast of Lake Baikal: Method of research and design / Yu.B. Khromov, V.A. Klyushin.
6. Vedenin Yu.A. Trends in the development of recreation in Russia in the new political and economic conditions / Yu.A. Vedenin, V.P. Kozlov // *Problems and programs of tourist and recreational use of natural and historical and cultural potential in the regions of Russia*. - M., 1995.- S.16-33., S.21.
7. Gidbut A. V. Proposals for the program of tourist development of the North of Russia / A. V. Gidbut, Yu. S. Putrik // *Problems and programs of tourist and recreational use of natural and historical and cultural potential in the regions of Russia*. -M., 1995. - S.98-115., S.100.
8. Shtogrin A. B. Fundamentals of management of tourist resources / A. B. Shtogrin // *Vestn. Moscow State University. Ser. 18, Sociology and Political Science*, - 2000 - No. 4-S. 128-135, p.131..
9. Khrabovchenko VV *Ecological tourism* / VV Khrabovchenko. - M. : Finance and statistics, 2004, - 207 p., P. 104 .. Lankar R. *Tourism marketing* / R. Lankar, R. Ollie. - M.: Economics, 1993. - 99 p., P.15.
10. Kabushkin N. I. *Management of tourism: textbook. allowance* / N. I. Kabushkin. -Mn. : BSEU, 2004.-644 p., P. 24 .. Alexandrova A. Yu. *International tourism: textbook. allowance for universities* / A. Yu. Aleksandrova. - M. : Aspect Press, 2001. - 464 p., P. 335.
11. Revinskiy I. A. Behavior of firms in the service market. *Tourism and travel: textbook. allowance* / I. A. Revinsky, L. S. Romanova. - Novosibirsk: Siberian Univ. Publishing House, 2001. - 304 p., p.19.
12. Nizamiev A. G. Features of tourism as a type of economic activity in Kyrgyzstan / A. G. Nizamiev // *Vest. Moscow State University. Ser. 6, Economics*, - 2003 - No. 4 - S. 74-83., S.78.
13. Lisauskaite Yu.V. Development of the tourist market in the Baikal region / Yu. V. Lisauskaite // *Geography and natural resources* - 2000. - No. 3. - P. 112-117., P. 15 ..
14. Sergeeva T. K. *Ecological tourism: textbook* / T. K. Sergeeva. - M. : Finance and statistics, 2004.- 360 p., P.280.